

Results of selective crop-cuts (4 m²) in a farmer's field near Chandina, Comilla District, Bangladesh, 29 Nov 1978.

Sample no.	Panicles (no./4 m ²)					Disease index			Yield (t/ha)
	Ufra 1	Ufra 2	Ufra 3	Whiteheads	Total	Ufra I	Ufra II	Ufra III	
1	9	45	42	10	140	6	32	30	0.15
2	13	32	58	2	147	9	22	39	0.35
3	8	40	35	5	198	4	20	18	0.51
4	7	26	78	23	220	3	12	35	0.54
5	4	19	196	6	284	1	7	69	0.85
6	7	13	77	9	236	3	6	33	0.88
7	1	2	111	7	346	0	1	32	1.42
8	0	4	69	9	305	0	1	23	1.70
9	0	0	116	20	536	0	0	22	2.92

All the panicles in each quadrat were harvested; classified as either Ufra 1, Ufra 2, ufra 3 (see preceding article), whiteheads (probably due to stem borer activity), or healthy; and counted. The disease indices ufra I, II, III were defined as the number of ufra I, ufra 2, and ufra 3, expressed as a percentage of the total number of panicles present in the specified area. Each crop was threshed to estimate yield corrected to 14% moisture content (see table).

Both Ufra I and ufra II increased more or less continuously, with yield loss up to severe levels of the disease. Ufra III first increased, then dwindled as the disease intensity (as measured by ufra I or ufra II) increased. Ufra III appears unsuitable as a disease index. Ufra II is suggested as a measure of disease level because it estimates a larger proportion of the yield loss directly at moderate disease levels, it assumes nonzero values at lower loss levels, and ufra 2 is easier to detect in the field than ufra 1. The disadvantages of using ufra II as a disease index are that, even at barely detectable levels, a substantial yield loss has already occurred (this is even more true of ufra I), and the symptom type ufra 2 resembles and may be confused with fungal sheath rot associated with *Sarocladium* spp.

But the loss of panicle density (panicles/m²) is the major component of the yield loss, about equal to the loss associated with the sum of all three symptom types. For any given disease level, half of the yield loss is represented by non-present panicles and half by panicles that produce no grain. Similar results were obtained in two other fields with distinct ufra patches at the same

site in 1977, and in three other fields at different locations in 1978 (one along the Dacca-Narsingdi Road, and two east

of Hajiganj, southern Comilla). No fields were examined in 1979 because of the difficulty of finding suitable ones. ■

Simulation of an ufra attack

P. C. Cox, L. Rahman, and M. A. Hannan, BRRI/Overseas Development Agency Deepwater Rice Pest Management Project, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Rangeladesh

Ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) is a serious disease of deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. To make progress in understanding the disease, it is important to be able to simulate natural infestation under controlled conditions. A special deepwater tank has been built at BRRI

for use in studying the disease. In 1979, the first year of the tank's use, an ufra patch in deepwater rice was successfully reproduced.

On 10 April 1979, the deepwater rice variety Gorcha was sown in an 8- x 8-m plot in the tank and simultaneously inoculated with 100 infested panicles kept from the previous season (1.6 panicles/m²). The plot was drenched with water from the main supply to the tank soon after sowing. The tank was flooded in early June and the water depth maintained at about 0.5 m. Every 2 weeks, a random sample of 100 stems was collected with the collector's eyes

closed. The percentage of infested stems and the average number of nematodes per stem (P) were estimated using the procedure described by Cox and Rahman (IRRN 4 [3]:10–11).

In early July, a field with plants showing symptoms of ufra attack (a faint chlorotic splash pattern on the young leaves), sown in early March, was found

at Matlab Bazar in south Comilla.

Samples were taken from this field on alternate weeks (see figure).

The percentage of infested stems first decreased as the water level rose from less than 0.3 m to more than 2.5 m. Some heavily infested stems were submerged, providing a source of nematodes for secondary infestation by waterborne

inoculum. After that, the growth of the percentage of infestation was similar in the tank and in the field. The 3-week lag between the 2 growth curves represents the difference in time of flooding. The growth in average number of nematodes per stem also corresponded closely. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice root weevil in Haryana

K. S. Kushwaha and S. K. Sharma,
Haryana Agricultural University, Rice
Research Station, Kaul 132021,
Kurukshetra District, India

The rice root weevil, formerly a minor pest, has destroyed rice crops in Haryana in the past 3–4 years.

The attack is mainly by *Hydronomolus molitor* Faust (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). Another allied species, *Bagous* sp., occurs with it. Its infestation of rice in India may be the first so far recorded. The grubs of the two species are similar in appearance, but the adults can easily be distinguished. *H. molitor* adults are shorter than *Bagous* adults (4.0–4.5 cm vs 4.5–5.0 cm long), and thicker.

These species and the white grub *Holotrichia insularis* Br. are comparable in nature of damage and life cycle. The grubs feed on rice roots from July to mid-September, then rest in the deeper soil layers during later months. They begin to attack within 2 weeks after transplanting in July, completely checking plant growth. Attacked plants do not tiller and remain stunted; their leaves turn yellow. Yield losses in attacked fields amount to 30–50% or more. Normally 1–2 grubs/plant in the initial growth stage will cause economic damage. Incidence is maximum in August. During the hot summer months the grubs are found in earthen cocoons, 14–30 cm deep, in compact soil. The adults emerge in June–July and feed on grasses in the absence of rice, then lay eggs in the rice fields.

Incidence of root weevils^a in Haryana, India.

Grubs (no./plant) in		
1977-78	1978-79	1979-80
14.2	18.1	4.2
13.7	11.3	7.9
18.9	24.7	3.2
17.3	10.7	5.4
15.1	15.8	4.2
14.5	14.8	4.0
13.8	7.1	5.1
21.4	14.2	5.8
17.4	19.4	4.5
14.3	17.5	4.2

^aAv, 9 plants.

The yearly grub incidence in August in fields near the Kaul Rice Research Station averaged 13.7–21.4 grubs/plant in 1977–78; 7.1–24.7 grubs/plant in 1978–79; and 3.2–7.9 grubs/plant in 1979–80 (see table). The lower incidence in 1979–80 may be attributed to drought that season.

The Commonwealth Institute of Entomology identified the insects. ■

Present and future gall midge control strategies in South China

*Shin-Foon Chiu, Plant Protection
Department, South China Agricultural
College, Kwangchow, China*

A change in the cropping patterns of South China to two or three rice crops per year has resulted in outbreaks of gall midge *Orseolia oryzae*. In the past when rice was not available year round, the gall midge overwintered as larvae in the weed *Leersia hexandra* and in wild rice *Oryzae rufipogon*. But gall midge survival on these alternate hosts was low and the gall midge problem was less.

Control strategies based on 5 years of experiments have been implemented over the past 2 years to significantly decrease gall midge damage. These strategies combine cultural control, chemical control, and conservation of natural enemies. The development of host plant resistance and population forecasting with pheromones is being studied.

Cultural control involves timing the rice crops during periods of the year when the relative humidity is unfavorable to the gall midge. A high relative humidity (about 94%) is essential for larvae to hatch and penetrate into the rice tissue. Periodic draining of the fields during periods of favorable relative humidity is practiced. The continuous rice cycle is also broken by crop rotation or the establishment of rice-free fallow periods. The overwintering weed *L. hexandra* is removed by hand from the fields and field borders during the fallow periods.

Chemical control involves spraying or dusting during the peak of adult emergence, the rice tillering stage. The most effective insecticides are pyridofenthion, diazinon, dimethoate mixed with trichlorfon, and pyrimoxythion (N-23) [0-0-diethyl-0 (2-methoxy-4-methyl-pyrimidyl-6, phosphorothionate)]. A seedling dip with 0.1% trichlorfon is generally recommended to conserve natural enemies of the gall midge.

Root-zone application and soil incorporation of granules are popular among rice farmers in Kwangtung, Kiangsu, and other provinces. Root-zone application of pyrimoxythion or carbofuran, either in the seedbed or the field, was effective and is safe to parasites